

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation Reactions in partially Aqueous Media : Oxidation of Hydrazides by Chloramine-T

A. Y. NIMBALKAR*, C. S. JOSHI and RAJARAM R. GAIKWAD

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 25 November 1988, revised 29 November 1989, accepted 7 May 1990

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of hydrazides by chloramine-T has been investigated in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium. The rate followed first order kinetics in [CAT] and [Hydrazide]. Effects of externally added reaction products and NaCl had no effect on the reaction. Effects of change in the dielectric constant and pH of the reaction medium on the rate have been also investigated. The rate constants for the rate-controlling step have been calculated as functions of temperature. The activation parameters have been computed using these constants. The mechanism in which chloramine-T reacts with hydrazides giving acyldiimide as an intermediate in the slow and rate-determining step has been proposed.

CHLORAMINE-T is used to oxidise many organic compounds¹. But it is not used in the field of hydrazide chemistry which plays very important role in medicinal and industrial fields² now a days. In continuation of our previous work³ we report here the kinetic investigation of oxidation of some substituted hydrazides by chloramine-T (CAT).

Experimental

Both the hydrazides were prepared by the well-known method⁴ and purified by repeated crystallisation. Chloramine-T and other chemicals were of analytical grade. Methanol (E. Merck) and double-distilled water were used. The kinetic procedure employed was the same as reported in literature⁵. The progress of reaction was monitored for two half-lives by iodometric estimation of the unreacted CAT at regular time intervals. The pseudo-first order rate constants were computed by the usual method (reproducible within $\pm 3\%$).

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of CAT-hydrazide reaction was determined by allowing reaction of CAT and hydrazide in different ratios to go to completion. It is observed that two molecules of hydrazides consumed two molecules of CAT.

where R represents $p\text{-CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4^-$ and $3,5\text{-(NO}_2)_2\text{.C}_6\text{H}_3^-$ in $p\text{-methoxybenzhydrazide}$ and $3,5\text{-}$

dinitrobenzhydrazide respectively. In end-product analysis⁶ the detections of $p\text{-toluenesulphonamide}$ and bis-hydrazide were done by pc and tlc. Nitrogen was tested by lime test⁷.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation were investigated at several $[\text{CAT}]_0$ and $[\text{Hydrazide}]_0$ in 50% (v/v) aqueous methanol medium. The plots of $\log ([\text{CAT}]_0/[\text{CAT}])$ vs time were linear upto 75% completion of the reaction and pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in $[\text{CAT}]_0$ establishing first order kinetics in $[\text{CAT}]_0$. Values of k increased with the increase of $[\text{Hydrazide}]_0$. Plots of $\log k$ vs $\log [\text{Hydrazides}]$ were linear with unit slope indicating a first order dependence of rate on the substrate concentration (Table 1). This order is also confirmed by Vant Hoff equation, i.e.

$$\text{order } n = \frac{\log [-dC_0/dt]_1 - \log [-dC_0/dt]_2}{\log [C_0]_1 - \log [C_0]_2} \quad (2)$$

Addition of NaCl had no effect on the rate. pH of the reaction mixture was varied from 8.50 to 9.50 and the reaction rate was found unaffected (Table 2). Addition of the reaction product $p\text{-toluenesulphonamide}$ had no influence on the rate. The decrease of dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition from 30/70 to 70/30 by volume (Table 2) decreased the rate. The rates were measured at different temperatures and activation parameters were computed (Table 1). Blank experiments performed showed that methanol was not oxidised by CAT under the experimental conditions.

Chloramine-T is analogous⁸ to bromamine-T and behaves like a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [OXIDANT], [HYDRAZIDE] AND TEMPERATURE ON REACTION RATE

Temp.=40° and pH=8.88 (unless otherwise specified)

[CAT] × 10 ⁴ M	[Hydrazide]* × 10 ³ M		k ₁ × 10 ² min ⁻¹		k ₂ ** × 10 ² min ⁻¹	
	3,5-DNBH	PMBH	3,5-DNBH	PMBH	3,5-DNBH	PMBH
5.00	1.00	4.00	3.05	1.24		
8.00	1.00	4.00	3.16	1.20		
10.00	1.00	4.00	3.16	1.18		
12.00	1.00	4.00	3.12	1.03		
15.00	1.00	4.00	2.84	1.11		
5.00	0.50	1.00	1.50	0.32		
5.00	1.00	2.00	3.05	0.69		
5.00	1.50	3.00	4.38	0.93		
5.00	2.00	4.00	6.13	1.24		
5.00	2.50	5.00	7.51	1.54		
5.00	1.00	4.00	1.88 ^a	0.51 ^a		
5.00	1.00	4.00	2.26 ^b	0.79 ^b		
5.00	1.00	4.00	3.05 ^c	1.24 ^c		
5.00	1.00	4.00	4.15 ^d	1.42 ^d		
5.00	1.00	4.00	5.29 ^e	2.00 ^e		

*3,5-DNBH=3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide ;
PMBH=*p*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide.

**Temp.=^a30°, ^b35°, ^c40°, ^d45° and ^e50°.

	3,5-DNBH	PMBH
E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	47.53	65.95
A (s ⁻¹)	4.27 × 10 ⁴	1.85 × 10 ⁷
ΔS [‡] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-127.2	-77.14
ΔH [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	45.85	63.34
ΔG [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	85.69	87.48

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION, SALT AND pH ON REACTION RATE

Temp.=40° and pH=8.88 (unless otherwise specified),

[CAT]=5 × 10⁻⁴ M, [3,5-DNBH]=1 × 10⁻³ M

[SALT]=NaCl × 10⁻³ M, [PMBH]=4 × 10⁻³ M

Methanol-H ₂ O %(v/v)	[NaCl] × 10 ³ M	pH	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹		k ₂ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹	
			[3,5-DNBH]	[PMBH]	[3,5-DNBH]	[PMBH]
70-30	—	8.88	2.43	0.88		
60-40	—	8.88	2.80	1.04		
50-50	—	8.88	3.05	1.24		
40-60	—	8.88	6.06	1.38		
30-70	—	8.88	—	1.64		
[3,5-DNBH] [PMBH]						
50-50	2.00	2.00	8.88	2.88	1.07	
50-50	4.00	4.00	8.88	3.03	1.20	
50-50	6.00	6.00	8.88	2.93	1.71	
50-50	8.00	8.00	8.88	3.28	1.28	
50-50	10.00	10.00	8.88	2.89	1.14	
50-50	—	9.55	2.81	1.17		
50-50	—	9.28	3.02	1.05		
50-50	—	8.88	3.05	1.24		
50-50	—	8.55	—	1.10		

dissociating as

And then the following equilibria are possible in case of CAT,

Finally, HOCl ionizes as

where R=*p*-CH₃.C₆H₄SO₂-

The possible oxidising species in chloramine-T solution are *p*-toluenesulphonamide, hypochlorite ion, molecular chlorine and chloramine-T itself. Addition of sodium chloride and *p*-toluenesulphonamide have no effect on the rate of this oxidation indicating that these species are not the oxidising species. The hypochlorite ion may not be involved otherwise the reaction would have been immeasurably fast. In case of BAT also the possibility of HOBr is ruled out⁹. Therefore, the oxidising species in this case is expected to be chloramine-T itself.

An increase in the amount of methanol in the solution decreases the polarity of the solvent (Table 2) and favours the process producing uncharged molecules from ions¹⁰.

Table 1 includes the kinetic data in the temperature range 30–50° and also the values of activation parameters. Fairly high positive values of free energy of activation (ΔG[‡]) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH[‡]) indicates that the transition state is highly solvated¹¹ while the large negative values of entropy of activation (ΔS[‡]) suggest the formation of rigid transition state.

On the basis of foregoing evidences the possible mechanism for the oxidation of hydrazides by chloramine-T may be formulated as

or the probable mechanism can be represented as follows :

where R is $p\text{-CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4$ and $3,5\text{-(NO}_2)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3$ and underlined species are unstable.

The following rate equation may be derived for the above mechanism in terms of consumption of [CAT],

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k[\text{CAT}][\text{Hydrazide}] \quad (12)$$

This rate law shows first order dependence on CAT and hydrazide.

References

- 1 H. M. K. NAIDU, S. N. KATGERI and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1185; S. P. MUSHRAN, R. SANEHI and M. G. AGRAWAL, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1972, **276**, 1161; M. C. MUSHRAN and S. P. MUSHRAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 262; C. SHRINIVASAN and K. PITUMANI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, **55**, 269.
- 2 T. S. GARDNER, E. WENIS and J. LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1514; *FARBENFABRIKEN BAYER 'A. G.*, Fr. Pat. 450 720/1965.
- 3 A. Y. NIMBALKAR, M. D. MALI, R. R. GAIKWAD and A. R. PATIL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 627.
- 4 P. A. S. SMITH, "Organic Reactions", ed ROGER ADAM, Wiley, New York, 1946, Vol. III, p. 367.
- 5 B. SINGH, A. K. SINGH, N. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 5203.
- 6 M. D. MALI, M. Phil. Dissertation, Shivaji University, 1987.
- 7 R. N. SINGH, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, 1977, **3**, 320.
- 8 E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 197.
- 9 F. F. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1973, 742; D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, S. ANANDA, M. B. MADEGOWDA and K. S. RANGAPPA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 323.
- 10 C. K. INGOLD, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, London, 1969, p. 457.
- 11 B. T. GOWDA and R. VIJAYALAKSHMI RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 467; B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 159; R. D. GILLIOM, "Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry", Addison-Wesley, London, 1970, p. 168; C. H. BAMFORD and C. F. H. TIPPER, "The Theory of Kinetics", Elsevier, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 315; D. ABBOTT, "An Introduction to Reaction Kinetics", Longmans Green, London, p. 102; I. M. CAMPBELL, "An Examples Course in Reaction Kinetics", Blackie, Glasgow, 1980, pp. 72, 77.